

Editorial Commentary

Charlatans are the scientists in today's world

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Abstract: With the advent of COVID-19, there was a surge of unrestrained research and review articles published in almost all mainstream journals. The information was almost the same; however, the sentences were paraphrased. The new information that was published in the lancet or nature would appear just in hours to other journals. I was shaken to the hilt when I saw people not specialized in microbiology or virology writing research and reviews on COVID-19. In this commentary, a succinct review was done on an article published in the Journal of Biomolecular Structure and Dynamics (JBSD). The author of the article had shown in a figure that the DPP4 receptor was the site for SARS-COV-2 entry to the host cell. The erratum was not published on the journal's website despite a long argumentative communication with the author and editor-in-chief of the journal. I leave the matter to the readers for their insight and judgment.

Keywords: Mohamed A. Hendaus, JBSD, DPP4 enzyme, COVID-19.

1. Introduction

Taylor & Francis publishes the Journal of Biomolecular Structure and Dynamics (JBSD). The journal was indexed in Thomson Reuters Science Citation Index (SCI), Scopus, and all the other rating agencies. According to the 2019 Journal Citation Report (JCR), the journal's impact factor used to be 3.549. In 2020, the JCR delisted the journal; therefore, the journal does not have any impact factor. The journal's current editor-in-chief is Prof. Ramaswamy H. Sarma from the University of Albany, Albany, NY, USA.

In late March 2020, I was looking for a vivid picture illustrating the mechanism of action of all the currently available drugs for coronavirus-19 treatment. While screening a hell of a lot of papers, an article struck my attention (1). The article was written by Mohamed A. Hendaus from Sidra Medicine, Doha, Qatar; Weill Cornell Medicine, Education City, Qatar, entitled, “*Remdesivir in the treatment of coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19): a simplified summary*” <https://doi.org/10.1080/07391102.2020.1767691>.

A quick look at the article shook me to the hilt. In the article, the author had illustrated a figure (Figure 2 in the article) mentioning the DPP4 enzyme as a platform for COVID-19 entry into the host cell. Unfortunately, the content of the article did not align with the journal's aims and objectives. The information was something best fitted with the health sciences journals. I decided to write an email to the editor in chief; Prof. Ramaswamy H. Sarma raising all these issues. I emailed him the following comments:

1. Coronaviruses are classified into SARS-CoV and MERS-CoV. The SARS-CoV binds with the ACE2 receptors for host cell entry, whereas; MERS-CoV enters into host cells after binding with DPP4 receptors. The COVID-19 comes in the category of SARS-CoV; therefore, it should bind with the ACE2 receptor, not the DPP4 receptor. Wherefrom, the author, did get the information that COVID-19 enters the host cells after

binding the DPP4 receptor? I have attached articles to support my statements (2, 3). I expect the same from the author.

2. Does the said article, “Remdesivir in the treatment of coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19): a simplified summary” qualify enough to be published in the Journal of Biomolecular Structure and Dynamics? JBSD is a highly reputed journal in structural biology, bioinformatics, virtual drug design, genomics, and biological networks.

I am here presenting the figure that mentioned the DPP4 receptor as a platform for the SARS-COV-2 entry into the host cell for the reader's interest.

Figure 2. Mode of infection of Covid-19 and Remdesivir mechanism of action. ER: Endoplasmic Reticulum; DPP4: Dipeptidyl peptidase-4.

Note: For originality check, please use identifier: <https://doi.org/10.1080/07391102.2020.1767691>.

In reply, the editor-in-chief (EIC) asked the author to analyze the paper critically and if there is a mistake in the figure, write an erratum. For my other question, “Does the content of the paper match the aims and objective of the journal?” The EIC replied, “On the peak of COVID-19, the publisher instructed us to publish any papers related to the COVID-19”. He also elaborated, “If such paper is submitted today, I will definitely reject.”

When I searched again, I found that in the month of October 2020, the same author published a paper in the same journal, and the content of the paper was better suited to the health sciences journals. In my opinion, October 2020 was not the peak of the COVID-19. How did the EIC allow the author to publish a paper which was not relevant to the journal's aim and objective?

The author explained the issue, "*Overall, the simplified draw was sketched in the early stages of being acquainted with COVID-19, and DPP4 was the best candidate at that time, extrapolating information from the coronavirus family*".

I leave the quote from the author to the readers. Where on earth did the author extrapolate the information that SARS-COVs (the family was discovered more than 20 years before) ever used the DPP4 platform to enter host cells? When I asked for the evidence, he sent me some references (4, 5). After carefully examining those articles, I found the author was misleading the EIC and me. The funniest thing is that the author on the first page of the said article under the section "Coronavirus (CoV) structure" writes, "*Moreover, the alveolar epithelial cells have ample expression of angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2), which is an aim by the virus. The detection of ACE2 by the S protein of the virus permits the invasion of the coronavirus into the human circulation system*".

The above statement shows that either the author was confused or in a state of delusion to tell the readers that where the mainstream researchers only focus on ACE2, he was the first to claim that COVID-19 enters host cells through DPP4.

When the author tried to misguide us by sending some irrelevant references (4, 5), I had no choice but to request the EIC to stop this communication as it was useless to have a scientific discussion with such an unprincipled author.

When we make mistakes, and definitely we make thousands of mistakes every day, the simplest way to

save ourselves is; simply confess our mistake. Till the day of my writing this commentary, no erratum was published in the journal. With error, the paper received mammoth citations in approximately three digits. The scientific community is in deep slumber, and charades are the scientists.

References:

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